

The Seventh-day Adventist Church in Nigeria

also known as "Adventists"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Protestant, Language, Protestantism, English

THE SEVENTH DAY ADVENTIST CHURCH IN NIGERIA Seventh-day Adventist (SDA) Church is a Sabbath Keeper and Protestant Christian denomination. made its entry into Nigeria in the year 1914 through efforts spearheaded by Elder David Caldwell Babcock who was born in New Hampshire, Ohio in United States of America on September 12, 1854. He arrived Nigeria with his family and missionaries: Dauphin, a Ghanaian and S. Morgues, a Sierra Leonean on March 7, 1914. Before his exit in 1918 as a result of ill health. Babcock had established three major branches in Erunmu (Oyo State), Shao (Kwara State) and Ipoti (Ekiti State). It was from these branches that the present branches were organised. The Church is largely represented in the South West, South East and North East Nigeria. In a 2018 census conducted by the church, it reported having 234,200 members across the three Union Conferences that make up the SDA Church in the country. Presently, membership of the Church has now grown to about 278,000 members across 282 local assemblies in the country. From the emergence of the SDA Church in Nigeria, Special attentions were paid to the establishments of elementary schools where people could learn how to read and write. It was a priority for the Church to establish training centres where early Church workers were trained. Shao became the first training ground for both Pastors and teachers. Additionally, this centre offered vocational skills, such as carpentry, bricklaying, woodwork and painting. As more souls were to the Church, new branches were opened and more schools. Presently, the Church has two universities (Babcock and Clifford), and many secondary and primary schools in Nigeria. As the Church kept on evangelising, it was planning to establish medical centres where people could get medical treatment. The structures, drugs and personnel were put in place to better the well being of the people. Statically, three medical centres were opened in Jengre (Northern Nigeria), Aba (Eastern Nigeria) and Ile-Ife (Western Nigeria). These were insufficient, hence, the need for more medical centres in Nigeria. The Church then opened more medical centres. Presently are many medical centres of which Babcock University Teaching is exceptionally impacting the whole Nigeria. The Church holds 28 fundamental beliefs that can be organised into six categories. These are: the doctrine of God, doctrines of man, salvation, church, Christian life and last day events. For a smooth administration in Nigeria, the Church this organigram. That is, Local Church, District, Conference and Union administrative offices. While local church oversees the running of the Church at the local level, the district coordinates the activities of the local churches within the same district. It is in the same manner that the conference supervises the works being carried out in the districts of the same jurisdiction. Presently, in Nigeria the has three unions (Northern Nigerian Union-Abuja, Eastern Nigerian Union-Aba and Western Nigerian Union-Lagos) these control all the activities of the conferences under their territory. References 1. Babalola, David O. in Encyclopaedia of Seventh Day Adventists on "Nigeria" Sourced from <https://encyclopedia.adventist.org/article?id=CC2R> retrieved on 18th January, 2024. 2. Alao, Dayo, ed. 90 Years of Adventism in Nigeria 1914-2004 A Compendium, Communication and PARL Department of Seventh-day Adventist Church, 2004. 3. Wogu, Chigemezi Nnadozie "Trailblazers of Adventism in Nigeria, 1900s - 1930s" in Journal of Adventist Mission Studies, Vol. 15 [2019], No. 2, Art. 3, Digital Commons, Andrews University, 2019 P. 14. Seventh Day Adventist Church in Nigeria - Facts and History retrieved on 18th January, 2024 from <https://> 5. Beliefs," Seventh-day Adventist Church, 2015, accessed from, www.adventist.org, accessed on July, 8, 2018, np.

Date Range: 1914 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Alao, Dayo, ed. 90 Years of Adventism in Nigeria 1914-2004 A Compendium, Communication and PARL Department of Seventh-day Adventist Church, 2004.
- Source 2: Wogu, Chigemezi Nnadozie “Trailblazers of Adventism in Nigeria, 1900s – 1930s” in Journal of Adventist Mission Studies, Vol. 15 [2019], No. 2, Art. 3, Digital Commons, Andrews University, 2019 P. 1
- Source 3: Agboola, D. T. Seventh-day Adventist History in West Africa (1888-1988): A Mustard Seed, Ibadan: LASOB Productions, 2001

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Babalola, David O. in Encyclopaedia of Seventh Day Adventists on “Nigeria” Sourced from <https://encyclopedia.adventist.org/article?id=CC2R> retrieved on 18th January, 2024.
- Source 1 Description: Seventh Day Adventist Church in Nigeria – Facts and History retrieved on 18th January, 2024 from <https://>
- Source 2 URL: Beliefs,” Seventh-day Adventist Church, 2015, accessed from, www.adventist.org, accessed on July, 8, 2018, np.
- Source 2 Description: Babalola, David O. in Encyclopaedia of Seventh Day Adventists on “Nigeria” Sourced from <https://encyclopedia.adventist.org/article?id=CC2R> retrieved on 18th January, 2024.
- Source 3 URL: Seventh Day Adventist Church in Nigeria – Facts and History retrieved on 18th January, 2024 from <https://>
- Source 3 Description: Beliefs,” Seventh-day Adventist Church, 2015, accessed from, www.adventist.org, accessed on July, 8, 2018, np.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/new-features.php>
Notes: The New King James Version of the Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group is in a secular nation of Nigeria so it relates with other religious groups within the boundaries of the nation.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is involved in proselytising in a nation of religious pluralism, the cultural contact is competitive.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is accommodating and pluralistic. The Seventh Day Adventist church is accommodating of other religious views.

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Though the cultural contact in Nigeria is not neutral, many of the religious groups go about their activities without engaging in confrontations with other religious groups with which they share the social space in the country.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There are violent conflicts between religious groups especially in Northern Nigeria.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group has programmes which has been put in place towards recruiting new members. They organise outreach programmes and evangelism campaigns towards expanding their membership in the country.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The religious professionals are expected not only to participate in the church proselytising but to lead such efforts.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: They are encouraged to participate in missionary work although it is not mandatory for all members to be actively involved. While some are able to physically attend such programmes, others support them financially and otherwise.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: Proselytising is not coercive by the group members.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The group does not have official political support in Nigeria.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: The church does not have the powers nor the tradition of punishing or prosecuting apostates.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: After attempts are made by the church to convince apostates to shun their scepticism of their former faith and it fails, they keep praying for them not to die in that condition but they consider them a social risk to the group. As a result, they ask members not to have anything to do with them so as not to get polluted by their foul and unwholesome beliefs.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They will ultimately receive divine punishment if they die in their renunciation of Christ.

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: They will be doomed and sent to everlasting punishment in Hades and hell if they die as apostates.

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 278000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.12

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group has recognised leaders from the local assembly level to the National (country wide) level

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Each local assembly has a pastor or leader who, with the support of other leaders in the assembly coordinates the affairs of the church.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Ideally, each religious community or local assembly has its leadership in place. Such leaders have the liberty to pilot the affairs of the church under the guidance of the Holy Spirit. No fully recognised local assembly is a surrogate of another but for administrative purposes, a group of churches in an area or region are grouped together to form a conference. This conference is coordinated by leaders who are usually more experienced from among the leaders in that region.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

Notes: https://mccsda.adventistafrica.org/uploaded_assets/9690-INTRODUCTION_TO_THE_ORGANIZATIONAL_STRUCTURE_AND_LOCAL_CHURCH_LEADERSHIP_IN_THE_S
thumbnail=original&1546164614 INTRODUCTION TO THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE AND LOCAL CHURCH LEADERSHIP IN THE SEVENTH-DAY ADVENTIST CHURCH

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: There are church elders and professional clergy among the church congregation. The professional clergy attend theological seminaries while the church elders do not necessarily obtain a strict form of pastoral training. The clergy are engaged by the church upon the completion of their training and placed in churches where they render their stewardship first unto God and to the community of believers.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: Political leaders are not involved in the selection of leaders for the church.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection

process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Followers do not often bring cases against their leaders though this may happen when the cases being the leader are grievous

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Other leaders in the religious group could make claims against another leader within their group.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Political leaders do not interfere with the running of the church.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The scriptures are not alterable. They have been canonised and cannot be altered by anyone. In fact, there is a curse placed on anyone who attempts an alteration of the content of the Holy Bible after its canonisation.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The church clergy are responsible for interpretation of the bible although there are still some allowance for believers who have the Holy Spirit within them to interact with the bible and interpret it as the Spirit gives them utterance.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

–Percentage: 50

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 100

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 40

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 20

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 40

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Objects

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

–At home

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Some of the religious centres are built in areas with nice vegetation. Trees are planted to provide shade and keep the church surrounding conducive for worship.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Spirit-body distinction is present in the church beliefs.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Since the spirit is said to outlive the body, it has qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that after this current life, death signals the beginning of an everlasting existence. This next form of existence is called the afterlife or eternal life. It is usually lived in one of two places; eternal life with God or eternal separation from God

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: The location of eternal life with God is usually referenced as being above the earth or in the skies while that of the eternal separation from god is in Hades.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes in the existence of supernatural beings. They believe that God is the head of the supernatural beings and he is good all the time. They equally hold the belief that Satan is His arch enemy. He always seeks to antagonise God and His desires but never seems able to win the challenges he orchestrates against his kingdom.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the existence of the supreme being who though cannot be seen with the physical eyes is believed upon as they claim that His works speak for Him.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - No
 - Notes: They only describe the supreme high God using anthropomorphic attributes. They speak of him as a God whose hands are mighty to save, as a God whose ways are past finding out and as a God who is powerful and mighty etc.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
 - Notes: The group does not limit the supreme high God to a sky deity though they believe that His abode is beyond the skies. They equally believe that he made the earth his footstool. They think of him as a transcendent God.
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: The group does not see the monarch more as a manifestation of the high God other than they see other humans. They believe that all mortals are made in the High God's image and that they all emanate from God.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They hold that the supreme high God is unquestionably good and that in him is no evil whatsoever.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: He is gracious, slow to wrath, plenteous in grace and mercy etc.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group holds that He has all knowledge of this world as He is said to be the creator of the world.
- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that darkness is not a hinderance to his sight. He is seen as a God who sees through the dark and in the dark.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The group says the high god is the discerner of the mind and the intent of the heart.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that he knows the end from the beginning so He knows what will happen in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that He has all the knowledge about the world in his hands as He is the creator, moulder and maker of the universe

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high God has deliberate causal efficacy in the world. They hold the view that He causes all things to be, he calls them into being and sustains the whole universe.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the power to reward and to punish rest with the

supreme being. They believe that he holds the moral compass of the universe and that He reserves the right to reward all humans with the recompense due them for all their deeds.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: They believe that both direct and indirect causal efficacy in the world rest with the supreme being

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: The group sees Him as a perfectly good God who exhibits only good attributes.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: The group believes he does this only when it becomes necessary to achieve a good end and to punish the evil deeds of men

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: The group sees Him as loving, kind, faithful and benevolent.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme being communicates with them through several means, including through religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes the supreme being communicates with the living through the bible, through his servants, through nature etc

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings the group believes exist and are loyal to the supreme being include angels, the twenty four elders, and other heavenly creatures. They also believe some non-human supernatural beings who are loyal to Satan also exist. These include demons and other wicked forces which work with them.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Men are not usually able to feel them but when they want to make their presence felt, they can activate whatever it takes to allow men feel their presence.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: The group believes that they have knowledge of past events which they have experienced in previous generations as they are essentially spirit beings who have lived over the years.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group believes they exhibits such negative emotions as anger, quest for revenge etc
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They have memories of past events
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings which are loyal to the supreme being are not strictly domain specific, however, those which are loyal to Satan, according to the group are a bit more specialised in their areas of operation. There are non-human supernatural beings which are deemed to be in charge of hills and mountains, there are those of the rivers and those which inhabit the forests etc

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural beings forbids some things and and sanction others. They hold the belief that engaging in the things they detest leads to unsavoury consequences.

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: They belief that certain places are sacred and should be treated with caution and respect

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is generally unacceptable in the religious group. It does not matter if it is the murder of a member of the group, a child or non-members of the group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: The group does not support sleeping with animals as it frowns at having carnal knowledge of minors

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The group supports that men honour the oaths they make to redeem them at the appropriate time.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that laziness offends the supreme being. They frown at anyone who exhibits laziness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: The group does not look kindly on gossips as they hold the view that they separate friends and sow enmity between people.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: They hold covetousness as an act that should be avoided because according to them, it offends the supreme being.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that the Supernatural being cares about everything that concerns his children. These include loyalty, group solidarity etc

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group believes that supernatural punishments are sometimes enforced to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group believes that political failure sometimes result from punishments for wrong doing.
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group believes that sicknesses and illnesses are sometimes result from punishments for wrong doing.
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: They believe that bad luck on descendants sometimes result from the wrongs of parents and grand parents.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the cause or purpose of supernatural rewards are known

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the high God and other supernatural beings are in charge of supernatural rewards

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural rewards are an essential part of the experience in the afterlife

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the bible saying that some people will be handsomely rewarded in the afterlife while others will receive moderate rewards, This is dependent on the quality of life they lived while on earth.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No

Notes: The group does not believe in re-incarnation.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Though the group believes that the Christ (the messiah) has come and gone back to prepare a place for the saints he is coming back to take them home. There are no messianic beliefs really but they look forward to the return of the messiah who will come to take them home.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: They need to preach to all human creation in the world to facilitate the eschaton

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: It will signal the beginning of the reign or kingdom of God

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Healthy life styles

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: The group teaches that men and women should have only one heterosexual partner to whom they are committed irrevocably.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: The group teaches that men and women should have only one heterosexual partner to whom they are committed irrevocably.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: They are not permitted to be involved in same sex marriages or in sexual affairs with animals.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Notes: They are not permitted to be involved in same sex marriages or in sexual affairs with animals.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice of any sort is promoted nor advocated by the group.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice of any sort is promoted nor advocated by the group.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice of any sort is promoted nor advocated by the group.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: This is a form of sharing or giving to the brethren. Though it is not mandatory, those who do this wisely and discreetly will have their rewards both here and in the afterlife.

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: This is not compulsory though

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: These include family prayer times and other religious activities done as a family.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Male children are circumcised in accordance with the tradition of many of the ethnic groups in the country.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– No

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The religious group is within the boundaries of a nation. This is therefore fitting to designate the society the group belongs to as a state.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Formal education is available to religious professionals in the religious group. The church has theological schools and seminaries where they train their clergy and equip them for church service. The formal education which the church provides is not restricted to religious professionals alone. The church established primary and secondary schools, they built and run

a school for training professional nurses. They also operate universities in Nigeria where they provide quality education to students so they could become productive members of the society.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The education the church provides is available to both male and female students across the country.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The church members interact with the church hierarchy whenever the need arises.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with government agencies and bureaucracies from time to time in the pursuit of their desires and ambitions.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are government agencies saddled with this responsibility across the nation.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government has the responsibility of providing portable water to the citizens of the country. Their effectiveness in doing this has not been optimal though.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are several privately owned businesses which provide transportation infrastructure to the citizenry in the country.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group interacts with the Nigeria Police Force which is under the purview of the Nigeria government.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This may apply to offences which attract capital punishment. Such matters would have been tried in a court of competent jurisdiction and the accused pronounced guilty. Then the judge would have to pronounce the punishment of the accused before execution can be carried out.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: This can only be carried out when the property so seized has been found to be proceeds of crime or if they were obtained under fraudulent circumstances.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The group plans her programmes following the Gregorian Calendar adopted for use in the country.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group buy their food items from markets around them. Some of them engage in small scale farming to cater for their families.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Seventh-day Adventist Church in Nigeria, Invalid csl-json to parse. Error: "The following required arguments are missing: family"

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